

USE OF ICT IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: This article examines the advantages and challenges of using ICT in Russian language lessons in technical universities, analyzes specific examples and offers recommendations for the effective implementation of these technologies in the educational process.

Keywords: Information and communication technologies (ICT), Russian language, technical universities, education, multimedia presentations, online platforms, videos, webinars, social networks, individualization of learning, student motivation, electronic textbooks, interactive tasks.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) play a key role in modern education, significantly changing teaching and learning methods. Their use is especially relevant in technical universities, where students, in addition to their basic technical training, must also master language and communication skills. The Russian language in this context acts not only as a means of communication, but also as a tool for a deeper understanding of professional literature, project development and scientific research.

ICT (information and communication technology) is a set of technologies associated with the use of computers and software to process, store and transmit information. In the educational field, ICT includes a variety of tools: from multimedia presentations and electronic textbooks to learning management systems and online platforms.

ICTs enable the creation of more interactive and dynamic learning environments. They contribute to:

- Increasing student motivation through the use of modern technologies.
- Deepening and expanding knowledge through access to a variety of information resources.
- Development of critical thinking and independent work skills.
- Improving the quality of teaching through the use of multimedia materials and interactive techniques.

The main goals of the Russian language course in technical universities are:

- Development of professional communication skills in students.
- Improving the culture of speech and written literacy.
- Mastering the scientific style of presentation and the ability to work with technical documentation.

- Developing the ability to conduct scientific research and prepare scientific publications.

Students at technical universities tend to focus on studying engineering and science disciplines. This imposes certain features on the process of teaching the Russian language:

The need to adapt educational material to the professional interests of students.

Using examples and tasks related to their future profession.

Introduction of specialized vocabulary and terminology.

The use of ICT in Russian language lessons helps to increase student motivation. Multimedia presentations, interactive tasks and videos make classes more interesting and dynamic. Technology allows students to participate in the learning process more actively and with greater enthusiasm.

ICT provides an opportunity to personalize learning. Online platforms and educational apps allow students to work at their own pace, review material, and complete additional assignments as needed. Teachers can easily track each student's progress and provide personalized guidance.

The Internet and digital libraries provide students with access to a huge number of educational resources: textbooks, scientific articles, video lectures and other materials. This is especially important for students of technical universities who require specialized literature and up-to-date information in their field.

The use of ICT helps students develop important skills such as critical thinking, information literacy, teamwork and communication skills. These skills are necessary in the modern world and are in demand in any professional activity.

Multimedia presentations allow teachers to illustrate their lectures, making them more visual and memorable. With the help of presentations, you can demonstrate images, graphs, diagrams, visual and audio materials, which helps to better understand and assimilate the educational material.

The use of video materials in Russian language lessons allows you to diversify the learning process and make it more interesting. Videos can be used to demonstrate correct pronunciation, analyze speech situations, explore cultural aspects, and even give virtual tours.

Online platforms and educational applications, such as Moodle , Coursera , Duolingo , allow you to organize the learning process in an interactive form. They provide access to a variety of learning materials, tests, assignments, and discussion forums to keep students actively engaged in the learning process.

Webinars and online conferences allow students to participate in lectures and seminars conducted by leading experts and scientists. This makes it possible to get acquainted with the latest achievements in the field of language and literature, discuss current issues and get answers to your questions.

Social networks and forums can be used to discuss educational material, exchange opinions and experiences, conduct online discussions and collaborate on projects. This helps develop communication skills and the ability to work in a team.

One of the main challenges of using ICT in education is technical problems. Incorrect operation of equipment, problems with the Internet connection and incompatibility of software can significantly complicate the learning process and reduce its effectiveness.

To use ICT effectively, teachers must have appropriate skills and knowledge. Not all teachers have sufficient training in ICT, which can lead to ineffective use of technology and insufficient integration of technology into the teaching process.

The use of ICT is associated with security and data protection issues. Teachers and students should be aware of the risks associated with the use of online resources and adhere to Internet safety and ethics.

One of the disadvantages of using ICT is the possible loss of personal communication between teacher and students. Virtual lessons and online learning may reduce interpersonal interactions and reduce opportunities for face-to-face communication and discussion.

It is necessary to organize systematic training of teachers in the use of ICT. Advanced training courses, seminars and trainings will help teachers master new technologies and integrate them into the educational process.

The development of high-quality educational materials adapted for use with ICT is required. Electronic textbooks, multimedia presentations, interactive tasks and tests should be developed taking into account the specifics of teaching the Russian language in technical universities.

It is necessary to provide educational institutions with modern technical infrastructure: computer classes, interactive whiteboards, high-speed Internet and software. This will create favorable conditions for the use of ICT in the educational process.

It is important to regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the use of ICT in Russian language lessons. This will allow problems and shortcomings to be identified and strategies to be developed to eliminate them and improve the quality of learning.

The use of ICT in Russian language lessons in technical universities opens up new opportunities for improving the quality of education. Modern technologies help to increase student motivation, individualize learning, access to a variety of resources and develop the necessary skills. However, to achieve maximum impact, a number of challenges related to technical problems, pedagogical training and safety issues must be overcome.

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